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Açar sözlər: Süni intellekt, müasir texnologiyalar, tətbiqlər, chat-boks, təlim prosesi, texnoloji inkişaf

Резюме: Роль искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в современном мире продолжает усиливаться, охватывая все более широкий спектр областей человеческой деятельности. ИИ уже зарекомендовал себя в медицине, производстве, маркетинге, творчестве и во многих других областях, включая образование. Технологический прогресс и непрерывное развитие искусственного интеллекта открывают возможности для создания более персонализированных и адаптивных подходов к обучению, которые учитывают индивидуальные особенности каждого студента. Основные задачи, которые решает ИИ, включают распознавание речи, компьютерное (техническое) зрение, перевод с разных языков и другие преобразования, связанные с любыми входными данными. Кроме преимуществ использования программ с искусственным интеллектом, есть и недостатки, которые подробно описываются в данной статье. Одним из самых распространённых рисков, связанных с ИИ, является то, что студенты пытаются представить работу, созданную ИИ, как свою собственную. Учителя и учебные заведения должны принимать меры для информирования студентов об опасностях и последствиях плагиата. Студентов также следует обучать тому, как конструктивно использовать ИИ и как правильно сослаться на контент, созданный и заимствованный из ИИ.

Xüsalə: Müasir dünyada süni intellektin (Sİ) rolu davamlı olaraq güclənir və insan fəaliyyətinin daha geniş sahələrini əhatə edir. Sİ artıq tibb, istehsalat, marketing, yaradıcılıq və təhsil də daxil olmaqla bir çox digər sahələrdə özünü göstərmişdir. Texnoloji inkişafa və süni intellektin davamlı inkişafına bağlı olaraq, hər bir tələbənin fərdi xüsusiyyətlərini nəzərə alan daha fərdiləşmiş və adaptiv öyrənmə yanaşmalarının yaradılması üçün imkanlar açılır. Sİ-nin həll etdiyi əsas məsələlərə səs tanıma, kompüter (texniki) görmə, təbii dillər arasında tərcümə və hər hansı giriş verilənləri ilə bağlı digər transformasiyalar daxildir. Süni intellekt proqramlarının istifadəsindən qaynaqlanan üstünlüklərdən əlavə, bu məqalədə ətraflı olaraq təsvir edilən çatışmazlıqlar da mövcuddur. Sİ ilə bağlı ən çox rast gəlinən risklərdən biri tələbələrin Sİ tərəfindən yaradılmış işi öz işi kimi təqdim etməyə çalışmasıdır. Müəllimlər və təhsil müəssisələri tələbələrə plagiatın təhlükələri və nəticələri haqqında məlumatlandırmaq üçün tədbirlər görməlidirlər. Tələbələrə həm də süni intellektdən konstruktiv istifadə etməyi və süni intellekt tərəfindən yaradılmış və alınmış məzmunu düzgün istinad etməyi öyrətmək lazımdır.

THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOLLS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

The role of artificial intelligence (AI) in the modern world continues to strengthen, involving an increasingly broad range of areas of human activity. AI has already established itself in medicine, manufacturing, marketing, creativity, and many other fields, including education.

Technological progress and the continuous development of artificial intelligence open up opportunities for creating more personalized and adaptive approaches to learning, which take into account the individual characteristics of each student. Thus, it can be assumed that in the near future, technologies related to AI will become an integral part of the education sector.

Originally the concept of AI (artificial intelligence) was coined by John McCarthy, who first used this term in 1956. He provided this definition: "It is the science and technology of creating intelligent machines, particularly intelligent computer programs." He noted that "artificial intelligence is related to the task of using computers to understand the workings of human intelligence, but it is not limited to the use of methods observed in biology" [McCarthy J.].

According to the explanatory dictionary on artificial intelligence, AI is a "scientific field in which tasks are set and solved regarding the hardware or software modeling of those types of human activities that are traditionally considered intellectual" [Аверкин А. Н., Гаазе-Рапопорт М. Г., Поспелов Д. А.].

The basic tasks that AI addresses include speech recognition, computer (technical) vision, translation between natural languages, and other mappings involving any input data. [Schroer A. Artificial Intelligence]. Currently, there are many separate areas in the study of AI that solve various tasks, including in the field of education. The implementation of AI in the field of education has numerous advantages, among which the personalization of education can be highlighted first. Modern AI-based technologies can adapt the educational process to the needs of each student, taking into account the pace of material assimilation, degree of understanding, and level of knowledge. It is important to note that AI is capable of analyzing large volumes of data, which allows for the identification of trends and patterns in learning, determining effective teaching methods, and even predicting potential difficulties that students may encounter.

A significant advantage for many educators is the ability to create their own educational solutions using AI, allowing not only to make the process of learning new

materials interactive but also to save a considerable amount of time. Regarding the lack of time, it is worth noting that artificial intelligence can take on part of the workload, including detailed grading of students' assignments, followed by providing detailed reports on each student's progress and identifying their weaknesses. In the future, this will enable educators to develop more accurate and effective teaching strategies. Despite many benefits, the introduction of artificial intelligence in the field of education is also associated with certain drawbacks and challenges, which manifest in the absence of human qualities. Morality, motivation, empathy, and individual understanding are excluded in direct interactions between learners and AI.

This can not only create significant difficulties for students in the process of mastering the material but also provoke various psychological problems. The lack of human qualities in AI gives rise to other issues. Creativity and critical thinking are important components of the learning process. AI algorithms can provide students with new information, but at the same time limit the development of their creative and analytical abilities. It is important not only to impart new knowledge to students but also to develop their ability to think creatively. The ethical aspects of using AI also raise many questions. The implementation of AI in education can raise numerous concerns about the privacy of teachers' and learners' data, as well as about the appropriateness of using technology for their assessment and monitoring.

There is one more problem concerned with AI is threat of job loss. Today, professionals in various fields are frightened of their future and are already advocating for the regulation of AI use. The usage of AI in the future in the field of education may raise concerns about the replacement of teaching activities by machines. Based on existing developments in AI and predictions from researchers at the Oxford Martin School, who predicted in 2013 that 47% of all jobs would be automated in the next 20 years, it can be said with a high degree of confidence that AI will indeed be able to independently perform some routine work tasks [Carl B. F., Michael A. O. *The Future of Employment*: p. 254–280.]. However, it is important to note that such technology will not be able to operate without the control of a specialist and the direction that they can provide.

Besides its disadvantages, AI should be considered a technology which has the potential to significantly improve the approach not only to the learning foreign languages but also to education as a whole. Nowadays, there are numerous solutions that already allow educators and learners to use AI in learning foreign languages.

Foremost, we can mention mobile applications and other applications based on AI for learning foreign languages.

One of the most popular apps is "Duolingo." It is used to personalize the learning of each user and offers using game elements to increase users' involvement or participation, i. e. a gamified approach to language learning. Another app, which also uses AI for personalization, is "Babbel," which is also offers educational courses at various levels and has a large database of words and phrases. The app. "Lingvist" uses AI to identify the user's weak points and offers exercises that can help improve specific skills. A similar function is performed by "Memrise," whose distinguishing feature is the personalization of exercises based on the user's interests. It also offers the opportunity to learn a language through video and audio materials. In conclusion, I would like to mention the app "Rosetta Stone," which allows the creation of personalized learning programs based on the user's language proficiency level. The app also offers the opportunity to learn the language through interactive exercises and games.

It should be stated that besides the apps and educational platforms, we can mention chatbots for learning foreign languages, which are an interesting and effective tool that combines technology and education. They are programs or chats in messengers that use artificial intelligence to interact with users in a dialogue format, resembling a conversation with a real partner in a foreign language.

For example, chatbot "Replika" ranks among the leading solutions of its kind, as it starts to adapt to the conversation partner during chats, later adopting their communication style. The main advantages of the chatbot are its high degree of personalization and the possibility for informal conversation. Another solution is the chatbot "Andy," which not only can support a conversation but also give the user certain tasks and then check their completion. Another solution, "Mondly," which is used not only for communication but also for practicing specific speech situations. The chatbot also contains a lot of conversational phrases and figures of speech. Uniting all these aforementioned features is the app "EF Hello," which, in addition to this, can also analyze the user's voice messages, offering the opportunity to work on pronunciation. A solution for elementary school students or preschoolers is

"MyBuddyAI," which is a virtual cartoon tutor that helps children develop their vocabulary in a playful way by repeating and memorizing words.

So AI can offer a lot of opportunities and benefits to teachers and learners. We should know that, with any new technology, risks and challenges appear. Before using any AI activity, we should consider carefully if it is appropriate for you and your learners or not.

One of the most common risks associated with AI is that students try to present AI work as their own. Teachers and institutions should continue to take measures to ensure students about the dangers and consequences of plagiarism. Learners should also be educated about how to use AI constructively and how to cite and acknowledge content that has been produced and taken from AI.

There is a common misconception that when you prompt generative AI for content, it goes to the internet and takes it from there. In most cases this isn't how generative AI works. Anything that it produced by AI is original, based on its analysis and synthesis of existing content. Submitting the same prompt twice can result in different outputs. As a result, the materials that AI produces for you aren't a breach of copyright.

Particularly when creating materials for classroom and commercial use, teachers should be aware of any copyright restrictions on the content that they create using AI tools.

Many AI tools that offer a free subscription in addition to their paid subscriptions restrict the use of content that has been produced using the free version. Always check the terms of use if you intend to distribute materials or content that you produce to make sure this is allowed.

There are many AI tools that enable the creation of voice, image and personas have the ability to copy or imitate real people. This creates ethical and, potentially, legal issues. Although it may seem like fun to create images or audios of famous people for use in learning activities, you should make it clear to learners that these aren't the actual people. Avoid attributing views or opinions to them that they may not hold. Likewise, creating images or videos of famous people should be clearly marked as the product of AI and should not be used as genuine representations.

There are some basic principles of AI use we should consider:

1. It should be stated that you and your learners retain agency, creativity and skills, and take an informed critical perspective. AI is not a magic tool, and it can make mistakes, and even produce work with bias in it.

2. You need to protect your own data and your learners' data as well as intellectual property. Don't input copyrighted data or identifiable personal information into AI tools.

3. Critically evaluate AI-generated content for bias, stereotypes and discrimination. Check its accuracy and that it's appropriate for your context.

4. It is important to protect teachers and learners from exposure to inappropriate content and ensure that they and their data are safe.

5. If you use AI tool, make it clear where it has been used. Do this by mentioning the AI tool used and the specific version or model. You can write something like, 'I used 'AI tool' to help with this work.' [Nik Peachey and Ross Crichton. 8-10].

However, it's important to remember that chatbots do not replace full-fledged communication with native speakers, but they can be a great complement to traditional learning methods. It is worth noting that the above lists only a number of solutions and scenarios for integrating AI into the process of learning foreign languages.

Thus, the study of the role and application of artificial intelligence in the field of foreign language learning highlights the significance of technological development in contemporary education. The use of artificial intelligence in this area offers numerous promising opportunities, such as a personalized approach to learning, more flexible and accessible methods of study, as well as more accurate monitoring and assessment of students' progress. In the long term, the integration of artificial intelligence into foreign language learning has the potential to transform educational practice. As algorithms improve and AI capabilities expand, we can expect more effective, accessible, and personalized methods for learning foreign languages for all students.

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